

The Effect of Image Quality on Automated Composite Defect Inspection

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Industrial Sponsor: Turlough McMahon, Jon Wright, Airbus.

The delivery of high-performance aircraft has driven the increase in rate targets. A promising rate-enabler is preforming of Non-Crimp Fabrics. Preforming over complex shapes can lead to defects, like wrinkles, reducing part quality. Using photographs to quantitatively analyse defects shows promise in reducing the cost of inspection. However, current implementations have yet to address the analysis bottleneck of photograph variability.

